

ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES BASED ON THE MOTIVATIONAL EDUCATION APPROACH

Alibekova Mahzuna

Gulistan State University

Junior teacher of the Department of English Literature

Annotation: The article discusses the features of the modernization of education using a motivational approach, which is expressed in activity-based practice-oriented learning. The key competencies identified in the framework of the work give a clear idea of the image of a higher education graduate, his or her general competence, readiness to solve non-standard tasks and adaptability to the constantly changing conditions of the modern world.

Keywords: education, competencies, subject-oriented education, educational programs, subjects of the natural science cycle, project work.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, cardinal transformations have taken place in the Uzbek education system. The processes of modernization and integration into the global educational system led to the inclusion of new provisions in the state educational standard, which, in turn, led to changes in curricula, educational programs and the introduction of new examination systems for the main state exam and unified state exam.

In this regard, the requirements for the results of mastering the general education program by students as a whole, for the level of formation of the necessary set of knowledge and competencies, skills of teaching and research, project and social activities, which contribute to further self-determination and informed career choice. The main task of modern education is to revise the traditional theoretically

oriented approaches to teaching, to introduce new educational technologies that make it possible to form the set of students' competencies (moral, general cultural, professional) that meet the needs of society and are necessary for further successful self-realization of the student [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analysis of the studied literature on the subject showed that the main difficulty in implementing the competency-based approach in teaching is the lack of methodological and practical base of many educational institutions, and as a result, the insufficient formation of these competencies among students, their unpreparedness for effective practical activities.

The characterization of the competencies presented in the article in relation to higher school age makes it possible to identify the main tasks for the successful implementation of educational programs based on the competency-based approach: the formation of professional and motivational competencies by including profile education (technical profile), the establishment of a content component of programs, as well determination of the effectiveness of implemented approaches through the use of testing methods.

In order to implement the tasks set, the authors turned to the experience of the boarding school for gifted students (Russia), Lehigh University (USA) and scientific and educational organizations in Asia, including Vietnam. On the basis of the described content, conclusions were drawn about the need and possibility of developing international training programs that will fully realize the required scope of competencies.

Modern psychology considers orientation as the most important property of a personality, which determines its entire mental makeup, starting with needs, interests, desires, inclinations, motives and ending with manifestations of abilities, character, volitional, intellectual and emotional characteristics. Orientation, thus, acts as an integral property of the personality, which regulates the social activity of a person, his behavior in general [2].

In a modified version of the methodology of B. Bass (A.A. Ershov), four types of personality orientation for managers are identified: on oneself, on business, on official subordination, on relations with people.

For students, three types of personality orientation are distinguished: on oneself, on business, on communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The motivational-target basis of educational and professional activity is a complex multilevel and multidimensional system.

One of the means of developing the motivational sphere of students was a specially organized project activity aimed at the formation of professional competence in the system of educational and professional integration.

Professional competence is a systemic dynamically developing personality characteristic (a set of abilities of knowledge, skills, business and personal qualities), showing the possession of modern technologies and methods for solving professional problems of various levels of complexity and allowing to carry out professional activities with high productivity [4].

The traditional approach, expressed in the need to “know”, is being replaced by a competency-based approach with the requirements to “act”, “be able”. Gradually, there is a kind of shift in emphasis from the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities to real practical experience in solving problems.

It is important to note that today much attention is paid to the development of students' professional competencies, the possession of which helps the student to make a purposeful and informed choice. In this regard, we analyzed the experience of educational institutions in Uzbekistan, Russia and the United States, which implement training programs based on a motivational approach.

So, each student is faced with the problem of choosing a profession in a priority area of knowledge, the direction of further activity. Studies show that only a small percentage of graduates (19%) are interested in technical fields of science [6]. The reason for this may be the poor formation of motivational competencies of

students in relation to the study of natural sciences. In order to increase interest in choosing this area of study, most Russian schools implement “subject-oriented education” programs in high school based on a competency-based approach. With regard to the technical direction, this approach is expressed in an increase in practical classes in physics, chemistry, mathematics, a system of non-traditional lessons is being implemented with the involvement of third-party organizations. There are also a number of lyceums for high school students working on the basis of technological universities.

The American experience in implementing a motivational approach to attract students to engineering specialties may also be of interest for the modernization of the Russian education system. In the United States, the practice of holding university-based summer schools for high school students is actively developed. The main goal of this direction is the need to prepare students for a conscious choice of a profession and increase interest in STEM disciplines (natural sciences, technology, engineering, mathematics). As an example, consider the Summer Program for Engineering Education at Lehigh University, Pennsylvania (USA). The key aspect of the program being implemented is the learning environment: students not only work together in teams, carry out practical and project activities, but also share life, participate in cultural events of the university. The head of the group - mentor organizes different types of work: laboratory, using advanced technologies and equipment of the university, practical, using problem-based learning methods, which make it possible to immerse yourself in the world of technological developments. The main objective of such programs is to improve professional knowledge. In the process of practice-oriented learning, critical thinking and personal responsibility for the ongoing project develop, a problem-based approach to learning is implemented, that is, those key competencies that are necessary in the implementation of further work activity are formed [3]. Group forms of work allow all students to go at the same level, keep up, and intermediate control points - meetings, assessment of the results of assignments - allow the mentor to understand

what actions are necessary to provide timely assistance to students. The result of the monthly internship was a research project implemented in groups, as well as testing, which showed that 90% of students (30 people) expressed a desire to enter universities in a technical direction.

Russian and American experience in the implementation of educational programs based on a competency-based approach may be of particular interest to numerous developing countries, the formation of the education system in which takes place under the significant influence of cooperation with Russia and the United States. One of these states is Vietnam. Thousands of students from this country are annually sent to the United States and Russia to study engineering programs. Stimulation of such academic mobility through the modernization of the educational system, the development of accessibility and popularization of international educational programs will contribute to the formation of a multicultural, highly moral, active personality that meets the needs of modern society.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the positive practical motivational experience of Russia and the United States presented in the work can be taken as the basis for the development of cooperation between educational organizations in different countries and the development of joint educational programs aimed at developing a wide range of competencies, including the intercultural aspect. As a result, the expansion of intercontinental boundaries in obtaining engineering education will increase the prestige of engineering specialties, develop international educational ties, strengthen friendly relations between nations and help people on the path of technological progress.

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